

SF₆ plasma surface engineered spent coffee ground derived carbon reinforced waste HDPE composites

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Low temperature Plasma Treatment

Surface Modification
(by etching or surface functionalization)

Various Gases are used (O_2 , Ar, CF_4 , SF_6 , Nitrogen and NH_3)

Rapidity, Simplicity, low expenses

- Modify physical and chemical properties without affecting bulk property.
- Improve surface wettability
- Improve interfacial adhesion between filler and polymer matrix

Spent Coffee Ground Waste

- 2nd most traded commodity after petroleum and 2nd largest beverage consumed next to water.
- 6 million tons of SCG are generated every year worldwide.
- Large volumes of oxygen required for decomposition process & releases methane.
- Ecofriendly and sustainable valorization plan is urgently needed to channelized this waste from dumping ground into commercial applications.
- Used as bio-based filler for many polymer composites, but the performance was not satisfactory for incompatibility with polymer matrix.
- Surface modification is required for interfacial interaction between the filler and polymer matrix.

Waste Walmart Bag (High Density Polyethylene (HDPE))

- 3rd most used thermoplastic polymer after PVC and PP.
- Widely used in water cans, milk bottles, storage bins, bags, etc. and causes accumulation of HDPE wastes.
- Mechanical recycling degrades different properties of HDPE.

Main Objective

- To improve different properties of carbon from waste spent coffee ground by low temperature Plasma surface modification.
- Reinforcement of surface modified carbon as fillers into waste High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) polymer matrix to enhance their thermal and mechanical properties.

Why Fluorination?

Materials and methods

Spent Coffee
Ground Waste

Pyrolyzed at
800°C for 2 hrs.

Heating rate
5°C/min

SF₆ plasma
treatment

5, 10, 15, 20
& 30 min

Carbon

Functionalization

Characterization

Filler

Improved
thermal and
mechanical
properties

Preliminary tested
for 3D printing
application

Filament
Composite

Polymer
Matrix

Waste
Walmart Bag

Plasma Etch PE-100 Equipment

RF Power: 150 watt
Frequency: 13.5 MHz
Vacuum Pressure: 0.5 Torr

FTIR and Raman spectra of Untreated and plasma treated Carbon

Figure 1: FTIR of Untreated and Plasma treated Carbon

Figure 2: Raman and variation of I_D/I_G ratio with plasma treatment time for Untreated and Plasma treated Carbon

- The strong band at 1138 cm^{-1} in FTIR indicates the semi-ionic C-F bonding, whereas the hump at 1220 cm^{-1} corresponds to covalent C-F bond.

XPS and TGA analysis of Untreated and plasma treated Carbon

Figure 3: XPS of Untreated and Plasma treated Carbon

Figure 4: TGA of Untreated and Plasma treated Carbon

Surface Micrograph of Untreated & plasma treated Carbon

Figure 5: Surface Micrograph of (a) Untreated Carbon, (b) 5 min, (c) 10 min, (d) 15 min, (e) 20 min and (f) 30 min SF_6 Plasma treated Carbon

EDS Analysis of Untreated and plasma treated Carbon

Figure 6 (a, b): Elemental mapping of 15 min plasma treated carbon.

Thermal Properties of Filament Composites

Sample	T _{onset} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)
WB	474	494
UTC	467	490
C-5	483	499
C-10	487	503
C-15	485	502
C-20	462	487
C-30	472	492

Figure 7: TGA of Extruded filaments

- T_{onset} and T_{max} delayed by 11°C and 9° for 15 min plasma treated carbon as filler.
- Similarly, T_{onset} and T_{max} delayed by 13°C and 8° for 10 min plasma treated carbon as filler.

Improved thermal stability

Mechanical Properties of Filament Composites

Figure 8: Tensile Test of Extruded filaments

- 15 min plasma treated carbon as filler exhibits highest improvement of 33.8% in tensile modulus and 13.97% in tensile strength.

Filament composites	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
WB	0.34±0.03	19.74 ±0.69
UTC	0.21±0.1	18.62 ±0.28
C-5	0.28 ±0.14	21.35 ±0.05
C-10	0.33 ±0.04	21.14 ±0.39
C-15	0.45±0.03	22.5 ±0.77
C-20	0.26±0.14	19.52 ±0.3
C-30	0.31 ±0.02	21.07±0.6

Fracture Surface Micrographs

Figure 9: Fracture surface of filament composites after tensile test: (a, b, c) WB (d, e, f) C-5 (g, h, i) C-10 (j, k, l) C-15 (m, n, o) C-20 (p, q, r) C-30.

Summary

- New functional group of -CF_2 and -CH_2 stretching band in the FTIR spectra of 15, 20 and 30 minutes of SF_6 plasma treated carbon samples indicates the effective functionalization.
- Existence of F 1s peak in the XPS spectra for plasma treated samples confirm the successful fluorination of the carbon samples by plasma treatment.
- Fluorine functionalization was also investigated from Raman, TGA and Surface micrograph analysis.
- Reduced thermal decomposition temperature, tensile strength and tensile modulus in filament composite with untreated carbon as filler than the neat polymer HDPE indicates the poor adhesion and interaction of Polymer and Filler matrix.
- Whereas improved thermal and mechanical properties observed for filament composites with 5, 10 and 15 min plasma treated carbon samples as filler.

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Thank You